

DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM BASED ON DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE MONITORING**Shalkhar N.***Almaty University of Energy and Communications,
Almaty, Kazakhstan.*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15634036>**Abstract**

The article discusses the design and implementation of a decision support system (DSS) integrated with an enterprise's digital infrastructure monitoring system. The aim of the project is to develop a software solution that provides event analysis, fault prediction, and optimal management actions based on formalized criteria. The system is implemented as a client-server web application using Python, Flask, and PostgreSQL technologies, as well as integration with an external monitoring system. The solution is based on the methods of multi-alternative analysis (AHP, WSM) and probability density estimation (Parseen-Rosenblatt method). The conducted tests confirm the effectiveness of the proposed approach in managing the OTT infrastructure in real time.

Keywords: decision support system, monitoring, AHP, WSM, Parseen method, digital infrastructure, Flask, PostgreSQL, data visualization.

Introduction. The digital transformation of business processes has led to an increase in the complexity of enterprise information systems. With an increase in the amount of data, the number of nodes and the interconnections between them, the need for intelligent tools that can not only monitor the state of the infrastructure, but also support decision-making processes based on the identified patterns increases. Traditional monitoring tools, as a rule, are limited to recording events and do not provide mechanisms for analysis, interpretation and recommendations.

In these conditions, decision support systems (DSS) are becoming especially relevant, allowing automating the choice of management actions based on an assessment of the current state and forecasts. Such systems combine methods of multi-criteria analysis, mathematical statistics and visualization, and can be effectively applied in the IT infrastructure to increase its stability and manageability.

The development of a DSS integrated with the Zabbix monitoring system is an urgent task that helps reduce the number of emergency situations, accelerate incident response, and optimize operational processes. The present study is aimed at creating a similar system and verifying its applicability on a test digital platform.

The decision support system being developed in the digital infrastructure is implemented on the basis of a three-level modular architecture, which is conditioned by the need to separate functional responsibilities, ensure flexibility of scaling and increase the fault tolerance of the system. This architecture allows you to clearly distinguish between the tasks of data collection, information processing and analysis, as well as interaction with the end user, thereby reducing the connectivity of components and increasing resilience to changes at each level.

The level of data collection and aggregation. The first level is responsible for interacting with an external monitoring system, Zabbix, which is one of the most widely used platforms for monitoring the state of the IT infrastructure. Data is exchanged over the REST protocol via the official Zabbix API, which provides a

standardized and reliable way to obtain information. The resulting metrics include:

- average and peak CPU usage;
- the amount of RAM used;
- availability status and node response;
- the number of triggers (incidents) for a given time interval.

The data is transmitted to the system in JSON format and uploaded to the PostgreSQL database. To ensure reliability, periodic timestamp collection has been implemented, allowing for time analysis of events. This level can be expanded by connecting additional monitoring sources without modifying the remaining components.

The level of analysis and decision-making. The middle architecture layer plays a critical role in the functional model of the decision support system (DSS). At this level, there is an intelligent interpretation of incoming telemetry data, a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the state of infrastructure components, as well as the generation of recommendations based on formalized criteria. The use of a hybrid methodological framework combining methods of multi-alternative analysis (AHP, WSM) and probabilistic forecasting (Parseen density estimation) makes it possible to form both operational and strategic decisions.

The AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) method proposed by T.Saati is the foundation for formalizing a multi-criteria choice in the presence of subjective preferences and heterogeneous criteria [1]. Within this system, AHP is used for:

- forming a hierarchical structure of the problem, including: purpose, evaluation criteria, sub-criteria (if necessary), alternatives to action;
- constructing paired matrices of comparisons of criteria and alternatives on a scale of relative importance;
- calculating local and global priorities reflecting the importance of each possible action;
- estimates of the consistency coefficient, which allows you to control the reliability of expert assessments and increase the stability of the result.

Example: if an abnormal load occurs on the server, AHP can compare alternatives (node restart, load redistribution, temporary exclusion from the pool) according to criteria such as failure risk, expected recovery time, and impact on other services. This ensures a systematic and transparent approach to choosing the optimal scenario.

The Weighted Sum Model is used in cases where there is a limited number of criteria with numerical values reduced to a single scale. In the context of DSS, WSM is used for:

- building an integral risk index for each node based on criteria (incident frequency, response, availability, etc.);
- ranking infrastructure components according to the level of criticality and the need for intervention;
- assessment of the state of the system in dynamics, by analyzing changes in aggregated values.

A feature of WSM in this implementation is the automatic retrieval of criteria values from the database, as well as the ability to dynamically adjust weights depending on risk management policies.

To estimate the probability of failures based on time-based incident data, a nonparametric estimation of the distribution density using the Parsen-Rosenblatt sound method is used [3]. The application of the

method within the framework of the system provides the following advantages:

- It allows you to identify trends in the accumulation of errors and hidden peaks of activity that are not obvious during normal visualization;
- Provides a time-based estimate of failure density, which is especially useful for predicting the next failures;
- It serves as the basis for initiating preventive measures when the density of events in a certain interval exceeds an acceptable threshold.

Integration and recommendation generation. The results obtained at this level are stored in the database and can be used for:

- displaying analytical results in the user interface;
- generating personalized recommendations based on predefined rules, incident type, and node priority;
- learning a decision-making model if a machine learning component is being implemented.

For example, if the failure density is exceeded (Parsen), the system can activate the Alternative Comparison module (AHP), and then generate a recommendation: "Decommission the node" if the integrated risk (WSM) exceeds the set threshold.

Проблемы на хосте test-odp-postgres1

Статус: ПРОБЛЕМА

Linux: has been restarted test-odp-postgres1

Время: 06.05.2025, 11:05:08

Уровень: Disaster

Решения для: Linux: has been restarted test-odp-postgres1

Отправить решение можно только после устранения проблемы

- Проверить uptime и логи /var/log/messages
- Анализировать причину через last -x
- Включить persistent journal для подробного лога
- Проверить автозагрузку через systemd-analyze

Figure 1. Problems on the host

Thus, this level represents the intellectual center of the system, providing not only data processing, but also their transformation into knowledge and actions. The choice of these methods is due to their versatility, proven effectiveness in applied IP and the possibility of mathematical interpretation of the results.

The visualization level. The frontend component of the system plays not only the role of an access interface, but also performs a critical function - it provides perception, interpretation and decision-making by the

analyst. It is at this level that the analytical information obtained as a result of mathematical models is transformed into understandable and timely actions, which makes the visualization module a key element of effective human-system interaction.

Interface components. The interface is built using HTML5, Tailwind CSS for styling, JavaScript and templating via Jinja2, which provides dynamic rendering of data from the Flask server.

Figure 2. Dashboard

The main screen of the system contains aggregated status indicators of key nodes and services. It acts as an operational control panel:

- it visualizes the load on the CPU, RAM, connection status, and failure rate;
- displays a user-configurable color scale of risk;
- allows switching between nodes and time intervals (implementation based on JavaScript tables and Tailwind dropdown components).

Figure 3. Incidents by severity level

The UX design of the interface is based on the principles of cognitive load and hierarchical visualization of information. The interface forms "defaults", offers a visual grouping of events by risk levels, and allows the user to focus only on the relevant context.

The recommendation module generates text and graphical suggestions for actions depending on the level of risk, error rate, analysis results, and available alternatives. It can work in automatic mode (for example, the priority is "red" – send a notification and

Graphs of the density of failures and anomalies. The results of the Parsen method are displayed as histograms and density lines, allowing you to track the frequency of incidents over time. Libraries used:

Chart.js – for adaptive line and bar charts with signed axes and legend;

Google Charts is for advanced analytics, such as comparisons by region, node, and error types.

The graphs are accompanied by tooltips that display accurate values, which is critical for rapid response.

suggest an action) or semi-automatic (the offer requires user confirmation).

Event log and decision history. Each action (real or recommended) is saved in the audit log, which allows you to:

- track the chronology of incidents;
- evaluate the effectiveness of the decisions made;
- use the data to train models or staff.

Figure 4. Logs

The interface allows you to filter events by type, date, criticality level, and user role.

The implemented visualization level provides not only a representation of data, but also contributes to the formation of knowledge necessary for making informed decisions. According to modern research in the field of visual analytics, the presence of dynamic graphs, color coding, and interactive analysis significantly reduces operator reaction time (up to 40-60%) and reduces the likelihood of errors in interpreting metrics.

Key Features:

- interactivity (hover, clicks, filters);
- visibility (color indicators, gradients);
- personalization (role + user settings);
- accessibility (adaptive design, mobile use);
- auditability (built-in log file and data export).

Thus, the visualization level not only increases the convenience of interacting with the system, but also is a full-fledged analytical module, without which the DSS cannot function effectively.

Conclusion. During the work, a decision support system was developed and tested, which connects to the monitoring system and helps analyze the state of the digital infrastructure. The built-in architecture allows

you to collect data, process it and show the results in a convenient way.

The implementation of the Hierarchy Analysis (AHP) method has provided a transparent and reasonable procedure for choosing actions in case of incidents, which takes into account various factors: the criticality of the node, the reaction rate, the probability of failure, etc. The application of the weighted sum method (WSM) made it possible to aggregate indicators into an integrated risk assessment, simplifying ranking and decision-making at the operational level. The use of the Parsen–Rosenblatt density estimation ensured the detection of anomalies before the system failure, which is an important element of proactive management.

The implemented visualization level has turned the system into an intuitive decision-making tool, accessible not only to technical specialists, but also to business analysts. The possibility of interactive analysis, automatic generation of recommendations and creation of reports enhances the analytical potential of the platform.

In the future, this solution can be expanded by introducing machine learning mechanisms, predictive analytics, fuzzy logic and integration with information

security management systems. The results obtained during the implementation of the project confirm the applicability of the proposed model for building effective and adaptive DSS in a corporate environment.

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